

Sn- and Mo-modified sulfonated carbons: properties and evaluation as catalysts for fructose conversion in water and DMSO

*Felyppe Markus Ribeiro Sobral Altino*¹, *Wander dos Santos Sá*¹, *Jailma Barros dos Santos*¹, *Wagner Alves Carvalho*^{2,*}, *Simoni Margareti Plentz Meneghetti*^{1,*}

Supplementary information

Figure S1 SEM (Field-Emission Scanning Electron Microscopy) analysis with EDX (Energy-Dispersive X-ray Spectroscopy) elemental mapping

Figure S2 N₂ adsorption–desorption isotherms for: C and CS_nx (A), CMo₃ and CSn₃Mo₃ (B), pore size distributions and average pore sizes for C and CS_nx (C) and for CMo₃ and CSn₃Mo₃ (D).

Figure S3 XRD patterns for CSn₃Mo₃ (before reaction and after reuse).

Figure S4 Visual aspects of the samples during the reaction, with and without the catalyst at 150 °C (0.5 to 6 h) in water.

Figure S5 Visual aspects of the samples during the reaction, using catalysts and without catalyst at 150 °C (0.5 to 6 h) in DMSO

Figure S6 Thermal profiles (TG/dTG) for CSn₃Mo₃ (before reaction and after reuse in water).

Figure S1 SEM (Field-Emission Scanning Electron Microscopy) analysis with EDX (Energy-Dispersive X-ray Spectroscopy) elemental mapping

Figure S2 N₂ adsorption–desorption isotherms for: C and CSn_x (A), CMo₃ and CSn₃Mo₃ (B), pore size distributions and average pore sizes for C and CSn_x (C) and for CMo₃ and CSn₃Mo₃ (D).

Figure S3 XRD patterns for CSn₃Mo₃ (before reaction and after reuse).

Figure S4 Visual aspects of the samples during the reaction, with and without the catalyst at 150 °C (0.5 to 6 h) in water.

Figure S5 Visual aspects of the samples during the reaction, using catalysts and without catalyst at 150 °C (0.5 to 6 h) in DMSO

Figure S6 Thermal profiles (TG/dTG) for CSn3Mo3 (before reaction and after reuse in water).